

**MODERN METHOD OF TEACHING RUSSIAN LANGUAGE AS A
FOREIGN LANGUAGE**

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Annotation: *This paper examines the latest technique of Russian language like a foreign language. Therefore there are some points why Russian language is to be taught to non philology students*

Key words: *learn, language, modern, Russian language, international students, foreign language, education*

A modern specialist is expected to meet new requirements in terms of education and competence, due to innovative processes taking place in various areas of modern society and, above all, in science and technology. These processes require higher education to search for new ways of upgrading and development. Modern university language education is aimed at upgrading RFL training system and at bringing it into conformity with European and Russian educational standards (Petrova, Kurbatova and Solyanik 2010). Russia is a modern country strengthening and expanding its political and economical positions internationally. For this reason, a growing number of international students want to attend Russian universities, and more and more students strive to master the Russian language as a means for receiving training in the chosen field of study. In Russian universities providing education to international students, RFL became an academic discipline in the 1950s and 1960s, and since then it has been developing, improving and searching for new ways of teaching the Russian language to international students (Pinevich 2011)

At present, almost every university having programs in the Humanities and other fields of study offers RFL courses. The Russian language is, along with the other academic disciplines, a compulsory course for international students taking university preparatory courses, for students pursuing specialist, bachelor, master and doctoral degrees, and for trainees. As a means for international and professional communication and the language of Russian science and technology, the Russian language is of great interest, first of all, to international students taking courses in non-humanities disciplines (Mets, Mitrofanova and Odintsova 1991). This field of study is referred to as “teaching the Russian language and other disciplines to international students, depending on their professional interests and needs in the Russian language and on the length of study” (Shtchukina 1990). The Russian language training is now taking place in the context of global changes within the entire education system: language learning goals, students’ needs and learning conditions have undergone major changes.

Research methods

1. Synthesis of best practices implies studying professional achievements by a number of creative teachers and highlighting the general and most important points, which further implementation leads to considerable increase in learning efficiency (Farisenkova 2003). Synthesis of experiences is a more advanced stage of knowledge acquisition than mere description of the experiences of specific teachers, since the objective of any methodology research consists in revealing training trends, which makes it possible to set up an efficient training system. In their turn, these common trends can only be revealed if multiple cases of dependence of learning outcomes on techniques in use are observed and analyzed. What is crucial is that these trends must be tracked in the work of various teachers and under different conditions.

2. The study of the history of methodology: The study of any phenomenon must be conducted by taking into consideration its historical development: it is impossible to understand what the phenomenon under investigation represents

today and what its prospects for development are without understanding how it appeared and developed.

3. The analytical description method (when studying and analyzing professional literature on the given topic, on linguistics, on the Russian and foreign language teaching techniques and on computer language acquisition).

4. Sociological teaching methods: (a) interviews with students attending preparatory courses and with master and doctoral students aimed at revealing their communication needs when studying RFL; (b) surveys conducted among international students with a view to identify their reasons and needs for studying RFL. A survey meets the precise objectives of the research study, corresponds to age-related peculiarities and possibilities of the surveyed students; some questions are multiple-choice questions, and some invite the surveyed person to provide his or her own answer; each proposed answer gives a different number of points, thus facilitating statistical and mathematical data processing. One of the advantages of surveying is that the data obtained in the process of using this method lends itself to easy quantitative treatment and is of high scientific value.

5. Combination of empirical and theoretical research methods: This means the study of language learning activities by international students taking RFL courses based on academic resources (academic articles, textbooks and professional study guides).

6. The statistical method has been used when processing and analyzing the survey results.

Today, Russian higher education institutions welcoming international students make valuable suggestions on how to teach Russian for professional purposes and develop educational materials fostering language training (Chuvaeva 2015). For university students enrolled in programs in non-humanities disciplines, the Russian language is a means for acquiring relevant professional knowledge, for familiarizing with Russian and international

scientific achievements and, as a result, for getting a degree in the chosen field of study. This is why modern programs, textbooks and study guides on the Russian language aim not only at providing students with linguistic knowledge of Russian, but also at teaching students to master written and oral Russian for use in real-life situations and to read professional literature in Russian (Kurova 2015). The present article focuses on teaching Russian to international prospective students in non-humanities disciplines and seeks to propose a theoretical and practical explanation as to why texts on fundamental science must be included in RFL teaching to non-philology students with a view to develop future specialists' professional competence in their academic discipline. The research results have elucidated the reasons why international students attending preparatory courses in Russian higher education institutions study the Russian language. A trial language learning program confirmed our hypothesis on fostering the study of the Russian language by prospective students on the basis of a comprehensive methodology underpinned by various specific aspects of teaching Russian as a foreign language to non-philology students. Our research has revealed the efficiency of this methodology in the formation and development of learners' language skills. The dynamic character of modern education requires constant updating and upgrading of specifications and guidelines for different Russian language proficiency levels. Today, a great many changes are taking place in education, related to the appearance of new groups of students, reduction of class hours, presence in the same classroom of students belonging to different age groups, increase in class sizes, learners' new communicative needs, etc. Accordingly, teaching methods, principles and educational tools are being updated, and new trends are emerging in RFL teaching. In any case, the teacher working with non-philology students needs to draw on the already accumulated teaching experience and to move further in search of new solutions in terms of content, management and linguistic methodology so as to foster the educational progress of students.

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